

Environmental Data Archival: Practices and Benefits crib sheet

Graham Parton
graham.parton@stfc.ac.uk

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Transmission, presentation and archiving of meteorological data

Technical problems with digital preservation

Digital Preservation cartoons covering key concepts of digital preservation:
Bit rot, Metadata, Obsolescence, data Migration, preservation planning

<http://www.openplanetsfoundation.org/community/media-centre/digiman>

MOLES Metadata Model:

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/moles>

NERC Metadata standard:

http://data-search.nerc.ac.uk/documents/metadastandard_v1.0.pdf

The research data lifecycle

Researchers are used to creating, processing and analysing data.

Data repositories generally have the job of preserving and giving access to data.

Third parties, or even the original researchers will reuse the data.

See <http://data-archive.ac.uk/create-manage/life-cycle> for more detail

What is a Dataset?

DataCite's definition

(http://www.datacite.org/sites/default/files/Business_Models_Principles_v1.0.pdf):

Dataset: "Recorded information, regardless of the form or medium on which it may be recorded including writings, films, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs, or other graphic representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow, charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing or computer programs (software), statistical records, and other research data." (from the U.S. National Institutes of Health (NIH) Grants Policy Statement via DataCite's Best Practice Guide for Data Citation).

A dataset is something that is:

- The result of a **defined process**
- **Scientifically meaningful**
- **Well-defined** (i.e. clear definition of what is in the dataset and what isn't)

“Publishing” versus “publishing” and “Open” versus “Closed”

Distinction between:

Publishing = publishing after some formal process which adds value for the consumer:

- e.g. PloS ONE type review, or
- EGU journal type public review or
- More traditional peer review.

and

- provides commitment to persistence

And **publishing**/serving = making available for consumption (e.g. on the web)

What do data centres do? on Lifecycle Model

The Digital Curation Centre's Curation Lifecycle Model provides a graphical, high-level overview of the stages required for successful curation and preservation of data from initial conceptualisation or receipt through the iterative curation cycle.

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-lifecycle-model>

Open Archive Information System (OAIS)

"**an archive**, consisting of an organization of people and systems, that has accepted the **responsibility to preserve information and make it available for a Designated Community**."

Where

"The information being maintained is deemed to **need Long Term Preservation**, even if the OAIS itself is not permanent. Long Term is long enough to be **concerned with the impacts of changing technologies, including support for new media and data formats**, or with a changing user community".

Open Archival Information System (OAIS)

SIP = Supplier Information Product
DIP = Dataset Information Product

AIP = Archive Information Product

Metadata for Discovery, Documentation, Definition

Lawrence et al 2009, [doi:10.1098/rsta.2008.0237](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2008.0237)